

Plectranthus madagascariensis Thicket Coleus

© M. Thompson

Group: Eudicot

Size: 1 m

Distribution:

Plectranthus madagascariensis occurs in the Eastern Cape and KwaZulu-Natal provinces of South Africa, to the Mascarene Islands in the Western Indian ocean. Plants are usually found in shaded subtropical thickets, on dry rocky outcrops and forest margins.

Importance:

Plectranthus species are used in traditional medicine for coughs, colds, and scabies, and their pungent foliage helps repel flies. They are hardy, water-wise, and widely cultivated locally and internationally as ornamental foliage plants, with variegated forms especially valued, contributing to their role in the bio-economy.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 38.75 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 32.04 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 1.18 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.6% [Single: 83.1%, Duplicated: 15.5%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 7 391.89 kilobases

Contig number: 509

Sample Contributor contact details:

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